

INNER-METALLIC COMPLEX SALTS OF SALICYLALDIMINO-ACIDS WITH POLYCYCLIC RINGS. PART I

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A number of complex compounds of bivalent copper, nickel, cobalt and manganese, and of trivalent iron, with salicylaldehyde and amino-acids like anthranilic acid, glycine and alanine have been prepared and their properties studied.

The configuration of these complexes cannot always be represented by unique and unambiguous structural formula. Preference has been given to the most probable of all the possible structures on the basis of their physical properties like solubility, colour and magnetic susceptibilities. The salicylaldehyde molecule in these complexes is believed to undergo condensation with amino-acids giving rise to what may be termed as "aldimine acids, which can function under suitable conditions as a tridentate molecule in co-ordination complexes. In some cases, they behave as bi-functional molecule with the carboxylic acid group remaining free. The composition and nature of the complexes have been found to depend on the nature of the central metal atom, as also on the nature of the addenda.

Pfeiffer and co-workers (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1931, 129, 163; *Annalen*, 1933, 503, 84; *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1936, 145, 243; 1938, 151, 145; 1940, 155, 77; 1942, 159, 313; Pfeiffer, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1940, 53, 93) in a series of papers have studied the preparation, properties and constitution of a large variety of inner metallic complexes of oxyaldimines and oxyketimines with spiral-like or polycyclic rings. In these, various *o*-oxyaldehydes and diketones were made to condense with monoamines, diamines, and even amides and esters of some amino-acids in presence of metallic salts. They also studied the inner metallic complex salts of salicylaldimine. A very significant observation was made by the authors in the case of bis-salicylaldehyde-cobalt ethylenediamine complex, which turns black from red in air by absorption of oxygen. The absorbed oxygen is again given off by heating the product in CO₂-atmosphere (Tsumaki, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1938, 12, 252). This catalytic oxidation has been studied in detail by Calvin and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2254, 2257, 2263, 2267, 2273) in recent years. This interesting chelate complex was synthesised on a large scale and used during the last global war as an effective oxygen carrier or artificial respiratory pigment under the name of *salcomine*. The present work was undertaken with a view to studying similar chelate complexes of copper, nickel, cobalt, manganese and iron with salicylaldehyde and different amino-acids like glycine, alanine, anthranilic acid, etc., as the free amino-acids have not been used by previous workers in the study of this type of chelate complexes. The salicylaldehyde molecule in these complexes is believed to have undergone condensation with amino-acids, which can function as a tridentate molecule under suitable conditions, and sometimes also as a bi-functional ligand with the carboxylic acid group remaining free.

The complex compound of copper salicylaldehyde with anthranilic acid was obtained by the interaction of copper anthranilate and salicylaldehyde in alkaline medium.

It is slightly soluble in water and readily in alcohol and other organic solvents like pyridine, acetone, etc. The anhydrous compound is, however, much less soluble. Copper salicylaldehyde-glycine and -alanine complexes were obtained by the interaction of copper disalicylaldehyde and the aqueous solution of the corresponding amino-acid. Both these compounds are soluble in water, but sparingly soluble in alcohol. They are slightly acidic to litmus. Similar complexes of nickel and cobalt were also prepared; with anthranilic acid nickel, however, gave a sodium salt in presence of caustic soda.

No manganese salicylaldehyde has been described in literature. This was, however, obtained from $MnCl_2, 4H_2O$ and salicylaldehyde in presence of caustic alkali. The product is readily oxidised by air at the room temperature, and a suspension of the substance in water is markedly blackened by the passage of air. Complexes of manganese salicylaldehyde with glycine and alanine have been prepared, though no corresponding complex with anthranilic acid could be isolated.

Ferrous sulphate, glycine and salicylaldehyde in aqueous alcoholic solution, on being heated for some hours, gave dark red shining crystals of a basic ferric salicylaldehyde-glycine complex, which resembles the corresponding copper and manganese compound in composition.

The constitution of these complexes can be represented as discussed below.

Copper Compounds

Copper-salicylaldehyde-anthranilate.—Copper combines with a molecule of salicylaldehyde and a molecule of anthranilic acid to form a four-covalent complex which may have the configuration (I), corresponding to that of salicylaldimine compounds and an alternative configuration might have been given by the structure (II):

The method of preparation with an excess of salicylaldehyde and the properties of the compound, however, support the structure (I). Its magnetic moment value of 1.79 Bohr differs from those of copper anthranilate ($1.92\mu_B$, cf. Rây and Sen, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 473) and copper salicylaldehyde ($1.92\mu_B$, cf. Tyson and Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1228). It can therefore be concluded that the copper salicylaldehyde anthranilate is a penetration complex with planar dsp^2 hybrid bonds (Rây and Sen, *loc. cit.*) having the configuration (I). A compound of the configuration (II), which may be viewed practically as an equimolecular mixture of copper salicylaldehyde and copper anthranilate would have possessed a magnetic moment of $1.92\mu_B$ per copper atom like that of its constituents.

Copper-salicylaldehyde-glycine.—The substance is derived from the condensation of two molecules of salicylaldehyde and three molecules of glycine with two atoms of copper. The probable configuration is given by

Its magnetic moment value of $1.82\mu_B$, and its high solubility in water are in support of the configuration given, in which copper is four-covalent with dsp^3 hybrid planar bonds.

Copper-salicylaldehyde-alanine.—This is formed by the condensation of two molecules of alanine and one molecule of salicylaldehyde with one atom of copper. Its configuration is best represented by structure (III).

The structure (IV) is not likely to be stable owing to steric conditions. The properties of the substance, particularly its high solubility in water, also exclude the configuration (V).

The moment value of $1.88\mu_B$ indicates that the copper is possibly present in a planar configuration with hybrid dsp^3 bonds.

Nickel Compounds

All the nickel compounds, described here, show paramagnetic moments of about $3\mu_B$ corresponding to the presence of two unpaired electrons. This indicates that the bonds in the complex are of the weak co-valent type resonating with ionic ones. They are coloured either green or blue.

Sodium Nickel - salicylaldehyde - anthranilate.—Two molecules of salicylaldehyde and three molecules of sodium anthranilate condense with a nickel atom to form the complex sodium salt, which can be represented by the octahedral configuration (I).

Nickel-salicylaldehyde-glycine.—This is formed by the condensation of two molecules of salicylaldehyde and two molecules of glycine with one atom of nickel. As the substance is insoluble in water and slightly soluble in organic solvents, its configuration is best represented by structure (II) in preference to (III).

Nickel-salicylaldehyde-alanine : (a, green).—One molecule of salicylaldehyde and one molecule of alanine condense with one atom of nickel to give rise to this green complex. As the substance is insoluble in water its configuration is represented by the structure (IV) in preference to (V). The latter may be viewed as a molecular compound of nickel salicylaldehyde and nickel alanine.

Nickel-salicylaldehyde-alanine : (b, blue).—This was derived from the condensation of two molecules of alanine and one molecule of salicylaldehyde with one atom of nickel. As the substance is soluble in water and organic solvents, it can be represented by configuration (VI).

The alternative structure (VII) is thereby excluded.

Cobalt Compounds

Cobalt-salicylaldehyde-anthranilate.—This is produced by the condensation of one molecule of anthranilic acid and one molecule of salicylaldehyde with one atom of cobalt. Its intense characteristic colour and the low moment value of $1.44 \mu_B$, corresponding practically to the spin moment of one unpaired electron, support the configuration (I) for the substance in preference to (II), which latter may be viewed as a molecular compound of cobalt salicylaldehyde and cobalt anthranilate.

The low moment value suggests that the cobaltous atom occurs in a penetration complex with dsp^3 planar bonds.

Cobalt-salicylaldehyde-glycine.—The compound is formed by the condensation of two molecules of glycine and one molecule of salicylaldehyde with one atom of cobalt. It gives a moment value of $2.89 \mu_B$, considerably less than the spin moment of three unpaired electrons usually present in a cobaltous ion. The substance is also soluble in water and possesses a characteristic deep brown colour. It may therefore be regarded as a penetration complex with planar dsp^2 bonds of the configuration (III) in preference to (IV) for steric consideration.

Cobalt-salicylaldehyde-alanine.—It resembles the corresponding green nickel alanine compound, being derived from the condensation of one molecule of alanine and one molecule of salicylaldehyde with one atom of cobalt. It gives a moment value of $4.59 \mu_B$, agreeing approximately with that for cobaltous ion. Hence, the bonds in the complex are likely to be of the weak co-valent type resonating with ionic ones. It should therefore be represented by a configuration similar to that of the green nickel alanine complex. The structure is also similar to that of the cobalt salicylaldehyde anthranilate, though the nature of the bond differs in the two.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Copper-salicylaldehyde-anthranilate.—About 2 g. of pure copper acetate was dissolved in the minimum quantity of water with the addition of 1 to 2 drops of glacial acetic acid. A solution of 2.72 g. of pure, recrystallised anthranilic acid in rectified spirit was added to the copper solution. Light green copper anthranilate was precipitated. The product was filtered, washed first with water, then with alcohol, and finally dried in air. The copper anthranilate was then suspended in alcohol and treated with 2.5 g. of pure salicylaldehyde. The resulting mixture was warmed on the water-bath and treated with less than its equivalent quantity of pure NaOH solution (0.64 g.), when a clear green solution was obtained. This was filtered hot and the filtrate, on standing, gave fine greenish blue crystals. These were filtered and recrystallised from alcohol. The crystals were dried in air. [Found: Cu, 18.23; N, 4.06; salicylaldehyde, 35.50; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 11.68. Cu (C₁₄H₉NO₂)₂·2.5H₂O requires Cu, 18.26; N, 4.04; salicylaldehyde, 35.35; H₂O, 12.94 per cent].

[Found (dried at 110°): Cu, 20.66; N, 4.52. Calc. Cu, 21.01; N, 4.64 per cent]. Only a part of the water is removed by drying.

Copper was estimated volumetrically after decomposition of the substance with H₂SO₄ (conc.) and a little HNO₃ (conc.). Nitrogen was estimated as usual by the Kjeldahl process after decomposition of the substance with concentrated H₂SO₄, with the addition of potassium sulphate and copper sulphate. Salicylaldehyde was estimated as copper salicylaldoxime, as described below.

To a known amount of the substance, 90. c.c. of a buffer solution (50. c.c. glacial acetic acid and 10 g. sodium acetate dissolved in 450. c.c. of water) was added, followed by 10 c.c. of 1% copper acetate solution. The mixture was stirred well and treated with a concentrated solution of 0.2 to 0.5 g. of hydroxylamine hydrochloride. The mixture was heated on the water-bath at 80°. The greenish yellow precipitate of copper salicylaldoxime was then filtered through a Gooch crucible, washed with hot water, and dried at 110°.

Copper salicylaldehyde anthranilate forms fine greenish blue crystals, slightly soluble in water, but readily in alcohol, pyridine and acetone. The solution of the substance is almost neutral to litmus and is decomposed by acids. It decomposes, on heating to about 120°, with separation of salicylaldehyde.

Copper-salicylaldehyde-glycine.—About 1.5 g. of pure copper salicylaldehyde was added to a solution of 2 g. of glycine in a little water. The mixture was shaken vigorously and warmed on the water-bath, and then filtered while hot. The filtrate, on standing, deposited shining blue needle-shaped crystals. These were washed first with water and then with alcohol. The product was recrystallised from water and dried in air. [Found: Cu, 22.58; N, 7.43; salicylaldehyde, 42.70; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 0.98. Cu₂(C₂₀H₁₉N₂O₈)·0.5H₂O requires Cu, 22.51; N, 7.45; salicylaldehyde, 43.24; H₂O, 1.60 per cent].

Thus only a part of the water is removed by drying at 110°.

The substance forms blue shining crystals, readily soluble in water, but practically insoluble in alcohol, acetone and chloroform. Its aqueous solution reacts acidic to litmus. It is decomposed by acids, but unaffected by alkalies.

Copper-salicylaldehyde-alanine.—About 2 g. of copper salicylaldehyde in alcoholic suspension was treated with an aqueous solution of 1.75 g. of alanine. The mixture was warmed on the water-bath, when a clear green solution was obtained. This was filtered. From the filtrate, on standing, shining crystals separated gradually. The crystals were first washed with water, then with alcohol and finally dried in air. [Found: Cu, 18.47; N, 8.20; salicylaldehyde, 35.05. $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)$ requires Cu, 18.49; N, 8.14; salicylaldehyde, 35.50 per cent].

The substance forms blue shining crystals, readily soluble in water, but sparingly soluble in acetone, chloroform and benzene and moderately in pyridine. Its aqueous solution reacts slightly acidic to litmus. It is decomposed by dilute mineral acids, but is unaffected by alkalies.

Nickel-salicylaldehyde-glycine.—About 3 g. of freshly prepared nickel salicylaldehyde in alcoholic suspension was treated with a solution of glycine (4 g.) in water. The mixture was warmed on the water-bath and filtered hot. The filtrate, on standing overnight, gave a crop of blue-violet crystals. These were washed first with cold water and then with alcohol, and finally dried in air. [Found: Ni, 14.07; N, 6.80; salicylaldehyde, 57.33. $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)$ requires Ni, 14.13; N, 6.74; salicylaldehyde, 58.83 per cent].

The substance forms blue-violet crystals, insoluble in water, alcohol and acetone, but very slightly soluble in pyridine. It is decomposed by mineral acids and strong alkalies, as also by boiling with water.

Nickel was estimated as nickel dimethylglyoxime after decomposition of the substance with concentrated H_2SO_4 and a little concentrated HNO_3 . Salicylaldehyde was estimated as copper salicylaldehyde as before.

Nickel-salicylaldehyde-alanine (green).—Freshly prepared nickel salicylaldehyde (4 g.) was treated in aqueous suspension with a solution of alanine (2.4 g.) in water. The resulting mixture was warmed on the water-bath. The insoluble product was filtered, washed first with water, then with rectified spirit, and finally dried in air. [Found: Ni, 22.35; N, 5.51; salicylaldehyde, 45.26; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 6.18. $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}_3)$, H_2O requires Ni, 21.92; N, 5.22; salicylaldehyde, 45.56; H_2O , 6.72 per cent]. Only a part of the water is removed by drying at 110° .

The substance forms shining green crystals, insoluble in cold water, but slightly soluble in warm water. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, but readily in pyridine and acetone. Mineral acids and strong alkalies decompose it.

Nickel-salicylaldehyde-alanine (blue).—Nickel salicylaldehyde (4 g.) in alcoholic solution was treated with solid alanine (3.75 g.) and warmed on the water-bath, when a bluish green solution was obtained. The solution was filtered while hot and the filtrate, on standing, gave fine light blue shining crystals, different from that obtained in the previous operation. The crystals were washed first with a little water, then with alcohol, and finally dried in air. The filtrate, on standing, gave a crop of shining light green crystals of the previous compound. [Found: Ni, 16.02; N, 7.63;

salicylaldehyde, 33.16. $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6)$, $1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 16.04; N, 7.66; salicylaldehyde, 33.46 per cent]. The substance loses only a part of its water at 110° .

Nickel-salicylaldehyde-anthranilate (Na-salt).—Nickel anthranilate, prepared from 4 g. of nickel acetate and anthranilic acid, was suspended in alcohol and treated with 2.95 g. of salicylaldehyde. The resulting mixture was warmed on the water-bath and treated with a slight excess of caustic soda. The solution was filtered while hot. The filtrate, on standing, deposited silky yellow crystals, which were recrystallised from alcohol. [Found: Ni, 7.76; N, 5.64; salicylaldehyde, 31.06; Na, 9.06. $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6)]\text{Na}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 7.74; N, 5.52; salicylaldehyde, 32.13; Na, 9.08 per cent]. The substance loses only a part of its water at 110° .

It forms silky yellow crystals, sparingly soluble in water, but fairly soluble in alcohol and acetone. Its solution is alkaline to litmus. The substance is decomposed by mineral acids.

Cobalt-salicylaldehyde-glycine.—About 4 g. of glycine, dissolved in a little water, was mixed with 3 g. of freshly prepared cobalt salicylaldehyde. The resulting mixture was thoroughly shaken, warmed on the water-bath, and then filtered while hot. The filtrate, on standing, gave violet-brown silky needles. These were washed first with water, then with alcohol, and finally dried in air. [Found: Co, 18.38; N, 8.72; salicylaldehyde, 38.24; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 2.49. $\text{Co}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6)$, $0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 18.40; N, 8.75; salicylaldehyde, 38.72; H_2O , 2.81 per cent].

The substance is soluble in water, but insoluble in alcohol and slightly soluble in pyridine and dioxane. Its aqueous solution reacts somewhat acidic to litmus. It is decomposed by mineral acids and strong alkalis.

Cobalt-salicylaldehyde-alanine.—Freshly prepared cobalt salicylaldehyde (3 g.) in alcoholic suspension was treated with alanine (2 g.) dissolved in a little water. The mixture was warmed on the water-bath, when the colour of the product changed to brick-red. This was then filtered, washed and dried as before. [Found: Co, 21.84; N, 5.35; salicylaldehyde, 45.44; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 6.14. $\text{Co}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3)$, H_2O requires Co, 22.01; N, 5.23; salicylaldehyde, 45.52; H_2O , 6.70 per cent]. The water therefore could not be completely removed by drying at 110° .

The substance forms brick-red crystals, insoluble in water, but slightly soluble in pyridine and acetone. It reacts neutral to litmus, and is decomposed by dilute mineral acids and strong alkalis.

Cobalt-salicylaldehyde Anthranilate.—Cobalt acetate (4 g.), dissolved in the minimum amount of water with the addition of 2 to 3 drops of glacial acetic acid, was treated with an alcoholic solution of pure anthranilic acid (4.45 g.). The precipitate of cobalt anthranilate, after being washed and dried, was suspended in alcohol and treated with salicylaldehyde (3.85 g.). The mixture was then warmed on the water-bath and treated with a solution of caustic soda (0.85 g. dissolved in a little water). The mixture was afterwards filtered while hot. On standing, brown needle-shaped silky crystals separated from the filtrate. These were recrystallised from alcohol and finally dried in air. [Found: Co, 18.57; N, 4.47; salicylaldehyde, 37.66; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 4.89. $\text{Co}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3)$, H_2O requires Co, 18.67; N, 4.43; salicylaldehyde, 38.62; H_2O , 5.71 per cent]. This indicates that only a part of the water was lost by drying at 110° .

The substance forms yellowish brown silky needles, sparingly soluble in water, but more soluble in alcohol and other organic solvents. When crystallised from pyridine it gave shining yellow scales which were found to contain pyridine. Its solution reacts almost neutral to litmus, and it is decomposed by mineral acids and strong alkalis.

Cobalt was estimated as CoSO_4 after decomposition of the substance with concentrated H_2SO_4 . Nitrogen and salicylaldehyde were estimated as before.

Manganese-salicylaldehyde.—About 3 g. of $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 4 g. of salicylaldehyde were mixed together in a conical flask, and the mixture was treated dropwise with a solution of caustic soda (0.4 g.). The yellow precipitate formed, was filtered, washed first with water, then with alcohol, and afterwards dried in air. The substance blackens slowly on exposure to air. [Found: Mn, 16.68; salicylaldehyde, 67.92. $\text{Mn}(\text{O}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CHO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mn, 16.51; salicylaldehyde, 73.27 per cent].

The results show that the substance could not be obtained in a pure state.

The substance is sparingly soluble in water and alcohol, but readily in pyridine. It turns black on passing air through its aqueous suspension. The substance is decomposed by mineral acids.

Manganese-salicylaldehyde-glycine.—About 3 g. of $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, dissolved in a little water, was treated with 4 g. of salicylaldehyde, followed by an excess of sodium acetate. About 2.45 g. of glycine was then added to the resulting yellow solution. A light yellow precipitate was obtained which was washed and dried as usual. [Found: Mn, 20.07; N, 7.56; salicylaldehyde, 44.25. $\text{Mn}_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6) \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mn, 20.07; N, 7.35; salicylaldehyde, 44.64 per cent].

The substance is insoluble in water and many organic solvents but soluble in pyridine and dioxane. It reacts slightly acidic to litmus. Dilute mineral acids, or acetic acid, and strong alkalis lead to its decomposition.

Manganese-salicylaldehyde-alanine.—Freshly prepared crude manganese salicylaldehyde (3 g.) in alcoholic suspension was treated with alanine (2.5 g.), dissolved in a little water. The mixture was warmed on the water-bath and the insoluble product was filtered. This was washed and dried as usual. [Found: Mn, 18.80; N, 7.03; salicylaldehyde, 41.88. $\text{Mn}_2(\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6) \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mn, 18.65; N, 7.12; salicylaldehyde, 41.66 per cent].

The substance forms yellow crystals, slightly soluble in water and alcohol, but readily in pyridine, acetone and dioxane. It reacts slightly acidic to litmus, and is decomposed by dilute mineral acids and strong alkalis.

Manganese was estimated gravimetrically as MnSO_4 after the ignition of the substance, followed by a treatment with HCl (conc.) and H_2SO_4 (conc.). Nitrogen and salicylaldehyde were estimated as in the previous cases.

Iron-salicylaldehyde-glycine (Ferric).—Freshly recrystallised $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, dissolved in a little water, was treated with glycine (1 g.), followed by the addition of an alcoholic solution of salicylaldehyde (0.75 g.). The resulting deep red solution was refluxed on the water-bath for about two hours. Dark red shining crystals gradually separated from the solution. The mixture was kept overnight in the cold. The crystals were then filtered, washed and dried as usual. A further crop was obtained from the mother-liquor by the addition of sodium acetate. [Found: Fe, 18.87; N, 7.02; sali-

cylaldehyde, 40.82. $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6)] \text{OH}, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Fe, 18.88; N, 7.08; salicylaldehyde, 41.14 per cent}.

The substance forms dark red shining crystals, soluble in water and alcohol, but readily in pyridine and methoxy-ethanol. It is, however, insoluble in acetone, dioxane, ether and other organic solvents. It reacts neutral to litmus, and is decomposed by dilute mineral acids and strong alkalies. It also decomposes in solution when heated. An acidified solution of the substance becomes colorless, but gives a blood-red coloration with potassium thiocyanate, indicating that the iron is present in the ferric state. This is also supported by magnetic measurement.

Iron was estimated volumetrically after decomposition of the substance with concentrated H_2SO_4 . Nitrogen and salicylaldehyde were estimated as before.

Magnetic Measurements

The magnetic susceptibilities of the substances were measured in a Gouy's balance with a field strength of 9.36×10^3 gauss, taking all the necessary precautions, as described in the previous papers. The results of measurements at 32° are tabulated below.

Name of the substance.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	$\delta \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$ (corr.)	μ_B (effective)
1. Copper-salicylaldehyde-anthranilate (green)	3.37	1172	-133.9	1306	1.79
2. Copper-salicylaldehyde-glycine (greenish blue)	4.49	2524	-201.0	2725	1.82
3. Copper-salicylaldehyde-alanine (blue)	3.81	1305	-149.0	1454	1.88
4. Nickel-salicylaldehyde-glycine (pale blue-violet)	9.01	3736	-175.7	3911	3.09
5. Nickel-salicylaldehyde-alanine (green)	14.59	3908	-108.0	4015	3.14
Nickel-salicylaldehyde-alanine (light blue)	8.06	2947	-166.0	3113	2.76
7. Nickel-salicylaldehyde-anthranilate (sodium) (greenish yellow)	6.07	4612	-352.6	4965	3.47
8. Cobalt-salicylaldehyde (orange-yellow)	25.15	8017	-144.4	8161	4.46
9. Cobalt-salicylaldehyde-glycine (brown-violet)	10.30	3296	-130.0	3426	4.50(T&A) 2.89
10. Cobalt-salicylaldehyde-alanine (brick-red)	32.70	8489	-108.0	8597	4.59
11. Cobalt-salicylaldehyde-anthranilate (yellowish brown)	2.26	712.9	-134.0	847	1.44
12. Manganese-salicylaldehyde-glycine (yellow)	50.30	27564	-216.6	27781	5.84
13. Manganese-salicylaldehyde-alanine (yellow)	50.30	30740	-261.0	31001	6.15
14. Iron-salicylaldehyde-glycine (dark red)	47.40	28250	-105.0	28355	5.91

δ = diamagnetic correction. T & A = Tyson and Adams, *loc. cit.*

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